

CONTRIBUTION OF K. KAMARAJAR EDUCATION AND POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT - A STUDY

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Abstract:

Kamaraj was popularly known as Kala Gandhi. He was considered to be having all the qualities of Gandhi. He was not fortunate enough to have a formal education or a rich ancestry or social background. Still he was adulated and had carved a name for himself in the pages of history. He was a man of his own making. It is a great wonder that a simple man like him had ascended to the pinnacle of glory and prominence. This phenomenon is a mystery to many. In India and many parts of the world democracy had catapulted many ordinary men who had sincerity, hard work and talents to come to the forefront in life. Kamaraj had started his life in dire circumstances. He had dedicated himself fully to the cause of national freedom movement. In 1920, at the young age of 16, he registered himself as member of the Congress Party. In the beginning he worked as a grass root level worker of the Party. He worked in the party with zeal and enthusiasm. He became adept in arranging political meetings addressed by popular party leaders. He used to welcome them and collected funds for the meetings. The hundi which Congress men carried to collect funds was called Gandhi hundi. Kamaraj used to carry the hundi and collected funds from the merchants and public in the area.

Key Words: Kamaraj and Gandhi, Kamarajar in Political Career, Educational Development, Industrial development

Introduction:

Kumaraswamy Kamaraj was a powerful Indian politician, activist and statesman who played an important role in pre and post-Independent politics. Born in a moderate middle-class family, Kamaraj's tryst with politics began early. His increasing interest in the country's political system finally culminated when he became a full time worker of the Congress during India's struggle for independence. Kamaraj's humble beginning did not deter him as he persistently worked to contribute actively to the Congress' struggle to overthrow the foreign rule. From being merely a campaigner, he rose to become a legislator in the Madras Presidency. The high point in his career came when he became the Chief Minister of Madras. Under his administration, Madras propelled forward and prospered. The education rate which was merely 7% rose to the magnanimous 37% with opening of new schools and education reforms. Irrigation and industry flourished making Madras one of the leaders of industrialization. Interestingly, Kamaraj continued to contribute even after his premiership, as President of the Indian National Congress. For his immense contribution,

Childhood & Early Life:

Kumaraswami Kamaraj was born on July 15, 1903 at Virudhunagar, Tamil Nadu to Kumaraswamy and Sivakami Ammaiar. His father was a merchant. He had a younger sister Nagammal. In 1907, Kamaraj enrolled at a traditional school. The following year, he enrolled at the Yenadhi Narayana Vidhya Salai but after a year of studies he shifted to Virudupatti High School. Tragedy struck young Kamaraj when he was merely six. His father died and his mother was forced to support her family. To help his mother, Kamaraj dropped out of school in 1914 to support his family.

Kamaraj and Gandhi:

Kamaraj came to know about Gandhi at the age of twelve. One of his friends Govinda Nadar who was also called as 'Bambai Annachi' was a businessman having trade contacts in all the major cities in North India. He used to travel to these cities quite often. When he returned to Virudhunagar he would narrate the major events that were happening in those cities. Once he had been to Bombay and had attended the 1915 Bombay Conference of the Congress Party. His vivid description of the happenings in the Conference and the detailed exposition on the speeches of leaders like Gopala Krishna Gokale, Loka Manya Bala Gangadhar Thilak, Motilal Nehru and Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi impressed young Kamaraj most. On regularly hearing the news of the freedom struggle Kamaraj began to have some kind of filial feeling towards the Congress Movement and its leaders. Since then he began to attend the meetings held in Virudhunagar at the behest of the Congress party.

Gandhi had affected Kamaraj both in his personal life and in public life. According to the dictates of Gandhi, Kamaraj had led a pure and simple life. Before Independence Kamaraj was a freedom fighter under the leadership of Gandhi. After Independence, he had co-operated with Jawaharlal Nehru who was the chosen heir of Gandhi. In 1954 when he became the Chief Minister of Madras State, he had implemented Gandhian ideals by making use of the administrative machinery. His administration was transparent, corrupt free and fully

committed to the welfare of the people. After the assassination of Gandhi, Kamaraj continued to cherish his ideals with inward love and faith.

Kamarajar in Political Career:

Kamaraj started his career doing odd jobs. He worked at his uncle's provision shop. It was during this time that Kamaraj developed interest in politics. He was an avid newspaper reader and kept himself updated with the current events. He soon became involved with the political processions and public meetings and acquainted himself with the Indian Home Rule Movement. The 1919 Jallianwala Bagh Massacre was a turning point in Kamaraj's life. The killing of innocent people instigated a rage of fury and vehemence in Kamaraj who decided to work actively in India's struggle for freedom and bring an end to British Raj.

Kamaraj's growing interest in politics was not supported by his family who sent him to Thiruvananthapuram where his second uncle stayed. However, Kamaraj's passion for politics could not be curtailed in Thiruvananthapuram as well. He participated in the Vaikom Satyagraha led by George Joseph of the Congress, against the atrocities of the higher caste Hindus on the Harijans. Kamaraj met Mahatma Gandhi, India's face of freedom struggle, at the Madurai's Congress meet. He was inspired by the latter's simplicity and non-violence movement. His political activities in Thiruvananthapuram annoyed his family to the point that he was called back. Though the elders in the family persuaded Kamaraj to stop getting involved in country's politics, it was without much result. They even tried to marry him off but Kamaraj resolutely disagreed.

In 1920, he joined Congress as a full time worker. He actively worked as political campaigner, organizing public meetings and carrying the Congress propaganda. Early in his career as a political activist, he participated in many events as a part of the Non-Violent Movement including the Nagpur Flag Satyagraha, Sword Satyagraha, Neil Statue Satyagraha and so on. After joining the Congress, he participated in almost all agitations and demonstrations against the British rule.

A pre-Independence party like the Congress which had nothing to offer to its cadres except suffering and imprisonment under the British rule, became the home for Kamaraj. With terrific energy and dedicated service Kamaraj converted the Congress into a formidable organisation in Tamilnadu. Himself a grass-root level worker, he became very popular among his party rank and file. He was imprisoned for the first time when he took part in the Salt Satyagraha undertaken by Gandhi. Later, participating in almost all the agitations he courted arrest and underwent long periods of imprisonment. His association with stalwarts in prison helped him broaden his outlook. He grew fond of books and through interactions with intellectuals in prison Kamaraj developed his leadership skills that proved a valuable asset to him as an administrator in later years of his life.

In 1930, Kamaraj participated in the Rajagopalachari-led Salt Satyagraha Movement in Vedaranyam. He was sentenced for two years. However, his term of imprisonment was cut short following the Gandhi-Irwin Pact that led to his release in 1931. In 1932, despite ban on public meetings and procession in Madras, he led processions and demonstrations which subsequently led to his arrest and one year imprisonment. In 1933, Kamaraj was yet again charged with involvement in the Virudhunagar bomb case. However, he was acquitted after not being found guilty. In 1936, Kamaraj's guru Satyamurti was elected President of the Provincial Congress. The latter appointed Kamaraj as the General Secretary. Four years later, the duo swapped positions strengthening the party base through their leadership skills. In 1942, he attended the All India Congress Meet in Bombay where Gandhi's Quit India Movement bore its roots. He spread the propaganda material to Trichy, Tanjore, Ranipet and Madurai and for the same was arrested and imprisoned for three years. During his term in jail, he read and self-educated himself.

He was imprisoned several times and spent ten years in prison. In 1930, Kamaraj participated in the Salt Satyagraha (Salt March), when Indians marched to Vedaranyam under the leadership of C. Rajagopalacharya as a protest against the British colonial rule of India. As a consequence, he was sent to Alipore Jail in Kolkatta and remained there for two years. When he was a suspect in a bomb blast case in Virudhunagar in 1933, George Joseph and Dr. P. Varadarajulu Naidu argued on Kamaraj's behalf and proved him to be innocent.

In 1937, he was elected to the Madras Legislative Assembly with no opposition. In 1940, when Kamarajar was on his way to Wardha to get approval of the Satyagrahis list, he was arrested and sent to jail by the British. While he was still in jail, he was elected as a Chairman of the Municipal Council in Virudunagar. Once he was released from jail, he walked directly to the municipality and submitted his resignation, saying that one should not accept any responsibility when he cannot do justice to it. In 1942, Kamarajar was arrested and sentenced to three years of imprisonment in Amaravathi prison. During his imprisonment, Kamarajar educated himself by reading books in jail. He went on to play an important role in Quit India Movement, Home Rule Movement and the Satyagraha movement among a host of other pre-independence struggles and boycotts. He was imprisoned close to six times, accumulating more than 3000 days, over 8 years in jail. Kamaraj was elected to the Madras Presidency legislature in 1937 and again in 1946. In 1936 he had been named general secretary of the Madras branch of the Congress Party, and in 1940 he became its president. In 1947 he was elevated to the Working Committee of the national party, and he remained associated with that group until 1969. He was also a member of the Constituent Assembly that in 1946 drafted the constitution for soon-to-be independent India. In

1951 Kamaraj contested and won a seat in the elections to the first Lok Sabha (lower chamber of the Indian parliament).

Kamarajar was made CM by defeating Rajagopalachari's alias Rajaji's candidate after Rajaji was forced to resign due to his infamous Caste (family) work based education policy. Kamaraj succeeded C. Rajgopalachari as the Chief Minister of Tamilnadu on April 13, 1954. Undoubtedly, this was a great achievement for him as he was the unanimous choice for the high office. He was honest and selfless to the core. And he occupied the post with distinction for ten years from 1954. Initially, there was opposition to his candidature as some criticised his poor educational background and said that he would not be able to fulfil his responsibility as Chief Minister, but his performance proved the critics wrong. During his tenure as the Chief Minister, Madras witnessed well-directed growth in the industrial and agricultural fields. A huge industrial estate, the biggest in Asia at that time, was established on the outskirts of Chennai. He was assisted by the Minister for Industries, Venkatraman, who later became the President of India

As a Chief Minister:

On 13 April 1954, Kamaraj became the Chief Minister of Madras Province. To everyone's surprise, Kamaraj nominated C. Subramaniam and M. Bhakthavatsalam, who had contested his leadership, to the newly formed cabinet.

As Chief Minister, Kamaraj removed the family vocation based hereditary Education Policy introduced by Rajaji. The State made immense strides in education and trade. New schools were opened, so that poor rural students had to walk no more than three kilometres to their nearest school. Better facilities were added to existing ones. No village remained without a primary school and no panchayat without a high school. Kamaraj strived to eradicate illiteracy by introducing free and compulsory education up to the eleventh standard. He introduced the Midday Meal Scheme to provide at least one meal per day to the lakhs of poor school children. Later it was expanded to four more schools. This was the precursor to the free noon meal schemes introduced by K. Kamaraj in 1960's and expanded by M. G. Ramachandran in the 1980s. He introduced free school uniforms to weed out caste, creed and class distinctions among young minds. During the British regime the education rate was only 7%. But after Kamaraj's reforms it reached 37%. Apart from increasing the number of schools, steps were taken to improve standards of education. To improve standards, the number of working days was increased from 180 to 200; unnecessary holidays were reduced; and syllabi were prepared to give opportunity to various abilities. Kamaraj and Bishnuram Medhi (Governor) took efforts to establish IIT Madras in 1959. Major irrigation schemes were planned in Kamaraj's period. Dams and irrigation canals were built across higher Bhavani, Mani Muthar, Aarani, Vaigai, Amaravathi, Sathanur, Krishnagiri, Pullambadi, Parambikulam and Neyyar among others. The Lower Bhavani Dam in Erode district brought 207,000 acres (840 km²) of land under cultivation. 45,000 acres (180 km²) of land benefited from canals constructed from the Mettur Dam. The Vaigai and Sathanur systems facilitated cultivation across thousands of acres of lands in Madurai and North Arcot districts respectively. Rs 30 crores were planned to be spent for Parambikulam River scheme, and 150 lakhs of acres of lands were brought under cultivation; one third of this (56 lakhs of acres of land) received a permanent irrigation facility. In 1957-61 1,628 tanks were de-silted under the Small Irrigation Scheme, and 2,000 wells were dug with outlets. Long-term loans with 25% subsidy were given to farmers. In addition farmers who had dry lands were given oil engines and electric pump sets on an installment basis. Industries with huge investments in crores of Rupees were started in his period: Neyveli Lignite Corporation, BHEL at Trichy, Manali Refinery, Hindustan raw photo film factory at Ooty, surgical instruments factory at Chennai, and a railway coach factory at Chennai were established. Industries such as paper, sugar, chemicals and cement took off during the period.

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Kumarasami Kamaraj Nadar is one such personality. He devoted his entire life to serving the country's people. His birthday falls on July 15, which is observed as 'Growth of Education Day' in recognition of his yeoman service in the field of youth education in Tamil Nadu. Young Kamaraj was however, inspired by Periyar E V Ramasamy. Though he rarely appeared with Periyar in public it was a fact that his opponents rightly identified Periyar as his mentor. The Independence struggle was in full swing in the country at that time. Kamaraj was eager to contribute his mite to the freedom movement. He was also concerned about the plight of his community of toddy tappers, which was then an untouchable community in Madras. Within a short time, he rose to become the leader of his and many similar communities by leading numerous local movements in and around Chennai for temple entry, school entry and other social justice concerns of untouchables. He was also inspired by Sree Narayan Guru's temple entry movement in Kerala. Atrocities, Kamaraj plunged headlong into the freedom movement. From then on there was no looking back for him. He became an able organiser in mobilising people for public meetings addressed by patriots. Appreciating his skill, Satyamurthi took him under his fold. In due course, Kamaraj, by his selfless devotion, rose in stature. Starting as Satyamurthi's personal assistant he ultimately rose to become the President of the Indian National Congress.

Kamaraj played a stellar role when India faced the crisis of three wars in the 60s. Immediately after the death of India's first Prime Minister, Kamaraj effectively mediated the transition of leadership to Lal Bahadur Shastri. After Shastri's untimely demise, thanks to his acumen and sagacity as the Congress president, he paved the way for Indira Gandhi to take on the mantle of Prime Minister. He had a larger-than-life image and many people wanted him to take over the governance. But selfless as he was, he placed the country before himself. Such was his honesty and commitment to the country.

He will forever be remembered in Tamil Nadu for his pioneering effort to ensure that education reached the poorest of the poor. He believed that only education had the power to break the man-made barriers of caste and creed. He took a census of schools in 17,000 villages in the State and found that nearly 6,000 villages had no schools. He initiated action to start primary schools in all these areas, appointed teachers and started the scheme of single teacher schools in remote places, if children couldn't go to school, the school should go to the children.

Kamaraj led a simple life and was the epitome of honesty and sincerity. His aged mother continued to live in the village even after he became Chief Minister. There was no water connection in her house and she continued to draw water from the public well. Some over-enthusiastic officials tried to provide the house with water connection as a favour, but Kamaraj heard about it and stopped them. He took a stand that though he was Chief Minister, he or his family should not be given any special privilege. They'd live like other citizens. What a contrast to the present day values of most of our politicians! He was a bachelor but embraced all children as his own. He understood the problems of people living in rural areas and the need for nourishment for growing children. He started the scheme of mid-day meals in schools, which served as a precursor to many such welfare schemes by governments in several States.

Educational Development:

Kamaraj was very particular in promoting primary school education. He wanted to motivate those depressed communities which were earlier denied the benefits of education. During his tour of villages to his dismay he saw the children were in a state of poor health due to poverty with poor vision, un-groomed hair without nourishment of oil, ill fed, scantily dressed and dwelling in insanitary huts. He realized that under such a situation the parents would care little about their child's education. For this purpose he had made primary education free¹³³. He had also ensured that villages with a population of 300 people should be provided with primary schools.¹³⁴ He also created single teacher schools in the villages and facilitated the unemployed youths to have jobs ¹³⁵. Even after this poor people in the country side hesitated to send their children to schools as they were also earning some money to add to the family income. Kamaraj thought about a plan to draw the children to schools. He thought that if mid-day meals were provided to the children in schools, the poor people may be motivated to send their children to schools rather than sending them to tend cattle or work in the farm. Mid-day meals scheme which was already in existence in a smaller proportion since 1925, was extended by Kamaraj to all villages and supported by government's munificence and subsidies. Kamaraj found out that the scheme was sound and workable. After the launch of the scheme, thousands of parents sent their children to schools. Kamaraj also expanded educational facilities to one and all. In 1951 ¹³³ Madras Information, March 1958/1963, January, 1955, there were 16,037 primary schools in the state. This rose to 30,554 in 1966. The number pupils on the rolls were 1852 million in 1951 increased to 3,558 million in 1961. In 1961, The number of children in the mid-day meals scheme was 888,000. The government's subsidy was to the extent of Rs. 8.278 millions. In 1966 the number of children under the mid-day meals programme had increased to 1,677,000 and the government's subsidy level had increased to Rs. 16.7 millions. The scheme had received wide support from the press, other state Governments and from Nehru himself. The Scheme was successful far beyond expectations. It became huge incentives for pupils to join the schools in large numbers. The wastage through

drop outs declined. The enrolment in schools increased in rural areas and also helped to break the caste barrier and led to a silent revolution¹³⁶. Many state governments followed the mid-day meals scheme of Kamaraj in their respective states. The American Government was very much impressed by the scheme and came forward to associate itself in the scheme. It sent milk powder packets through their CARE Programme. Besides, free books, slates and dresses for the poor children attending school were distributed by the Government. Kamaraj's contribution to the cause of education in Tamilnadu was immense. First, as soon he had assumed office he had withdrawn the Rajagopalachari's educational reform. That act generated groundswell of welcome from the people¹³⁷. Besides the mid- 136 Madras Information, March 1963,. Also see, N.D. Sundaravadivelu, Kamaraj, Third Edition (Madras, 1989),. 137 The Hindu, 19th May 1954. day meals scheme, he had also introduced free uniforms scheme¹³⁸. A scheme was formulated to provide free uniforms to poor school children. This was carried out at the instance of Kamaraj who had wanted to eschew discrimination of school children on the basis of their being poor or rich. This move had helped to erase the inferiority complex from the minds of the poor children. In 1966, 940,000 children were the beneficiaries of the Scheme. For carrying out very many improvements in the schools he had mobilized voluntary donations from the public which swelled to the tune of Rs.80, 000 millions. With this generous fund schools in Tamilnadu were improved in very many directions such as repairs to buildings, additions to school equipments, better furniture and additional facilities for children¹³⁹. Kamaraj had declared in 1960 that poor children would get free education up to the secondary school level. He saw to it that there was no village in Tamilnadu without a primary school. He also took efforts to improve the standard of education also. Because of this he was hailed by one and all as one who had brought literacy to Tamilnadu. The government also built houses for the village teachers to reside in the villages as competent teachers shied away from working in rural schools for want of facilities. Poor students on admission to professional courses were given interest free educational loans repayable in installments later. Kamaraj's reign saw a healthy growth of arts colleges, two physical education colleges, 10 teachers training colleges, and 39 teachers' training schools. New schools within a perimeter of five miles from the residences of the students were opened. The teachers began to enjoy sound 138 V.K. Narasimhan, op. cit., 139 Madras Information, February 1963, pension scheme, provident fund and had compulsory saving schemes 140. Under Kamaraj's stewardship of the State, Tamilnadu had made a notable progress on all sectors viz., food, agriculture, industry, education, power, irrigation and roads. Kamaraj's rule was lauded by one and all as the Golden Rule of Kamaraj.

In 1954, he was elected as the Chief Minister of the Madras State. He reluctantly took up the post and nominated his co-contestants C. Subramaniam and M. Bhakthavatsalam in his cabinet. Kamaraj's motto as Chief Minister was to work for the welfare of the people. Under Kamaraj, Madras made immense progress in education and trade. New schools were opened and education was made free and compulsory for all up to 11th Standard. Every village had a primary school and every Panchayat a high school. He even introduced the concept of Mid-Day Meal Scheme for lakhs of poor and deprived children. To eradicate caste, creed and class differences, he introduced school uniform. Such was the progress under his administration that the education rate augmented from merely 7% to 37%. Education was the primary focus of Kamaraj's Government but he did not overlook other sectors. In fact, he came up with major irrigation schemes that led to the building of dams and canals. Farmers were given facilities and subsidized loans. He also administered the setting up of major industries under his governance such as Neyveli Lignite Corporation, BHEL, Manali Oil Refinery, Hindustan raw photo film factory, surgical instruments factory, a railway coach factory and so on. Industries such as paper, sugar, chemicals and cement were also established during this period.

Kamaraj may not have had formal education. He may not have had a college degree. But he was instrumental in revolutionary reforms and infrastructure for education in Tamil Nadu. Primary, secondary, tertiary and higher education registered phenomenal growth thanks to the strong foundation he laid. Having a skill gives the youth confidence and self esteem, which are essential for personality growth. Self esteem cannot be given. But what we can do is help them attain it. How, you ask? Give them a task that they think they cannot do. And tell them to work on it until they get it done without giving up. When they finish the task, they would have found true self esteem. There is a statue of Kamaraj in Chennai. But unlike statues of most famous personalities, this is not a stand alone. On either side of the leader, are a boy and a girl holding his hand. This shows the kind of person he was while he was alive – a compassionate man, a leader and a guiding light. He is renowned to be the greatest Chief Minister that Tamil Nadu ever had; or even one of the greatest Chief Minister any Indian state had ever had. The kingmaker of Indian politics for over two decades and known for his simple and frugal living and demeanour, he is responsible for a significant part of the development that Tamil Nadu underwent so far. He was awarded India's highest civilian honour, the Bharat Ratna, posthumously in 1976.

Industrial Development:

Kamaraj was keen on the industrial development of the state in a big way. Because of his tremendous zeal and energy he was able to establish a big aluminum plant and a large sized paper mill in the state. Neyveli Lignite Scheme, Raw Photo Film Industry at Nilgiri, Surgical instruments Factory at Guindy, Sugar Factories, Bi-Carbonate Factories, Cement Factories, Railway coach Factory at Avadi and Mettur Paper Industry, were started in the regime of Kamaraj. On realizing the importance and the employment potential they would

generate he had helped these industries with a grant of Rs. one crore for each without any misgivings. Kamaraj took effort to start co-operative and private spinning mills at Coimbatore and made Coimbatore city to be called as the Manchester of Tamilnadu (India). Madras state co-operative industrial Bank was established by the state government in 1958. This encouraged the creation of co-operative units for developments of Handy Crafts and others. Nearly 365 co-operative societies were also started. In 1963 in the Madras state there were 6,365 industries of different types and 3,52,563 workers were working in them. Thus the state net with a planned development. Due to the industrial policies and activities of Kamaraj Madras state occupied the third place among the Indian states. The small ministry as given below assisted him a lot in launching many programs successfully and effectively. His ministry in 1954 consisted eight in 1957 also eight ministers and in 1962 nine ministers. Kamaraj's goal was to improve the economic conditions of the farmers by the development of agricultural sector and to augment their income in a big way. But he considered it a long term goal under the then prevailing circumstances. But the farmers after the advent of freedom and the establishment of popular governments expected facilities and amenities right away to raise their standard of living. Kamaraj felt that with the available resources with the government it would not be possible to increase the standard of living of the rural masses overnight. However, amenities like schools, hospitals, roads, drinking water availability, electricity and irrigation could be extended to the rural people. These basic amenities would help for making further improvements in the standard of living of the rural people.

Conclusion:

A person or administrator may die one day but their name presence is so important in this way his name has been written in all syllabus of Tamilnadu education board, social service board, achievement board and remarkable leader's board in Tamilnadu political history. Before Independence Kamaraj was a freedom fighter under the leadership of Gandhi. After Independence, he had co-operated with Jawaharlal Nehru who was the chosen heir of Gandhi. In 1954 when he became the Chief Minister of Madras State, he had implemented Gandhian ideals by making use of the administrative machinery. His administration was transparent, corrupt free and fully committed to the welfare of the people. After the assassination of Gandhi, Kamaraj continued to cherish his ideals with inward love and faith. All these praiseworthy names and characters came to him owing to his marvelous, splendid, luminous, esthetic, sparkling and holy attitude of Perunthalaivar K. Kamaraj in southern region in Tamilnadu politics. Still he has been role model of so many young students, politicians, administrator, workers and others because his genuine and good administration during his political power got to him all these good characters and names. Kamaraj as a person and a personality, in literature, has been studied as a King Maker and a seasoned diplomat in both regional and national politics or an educational philanthropist or an uneducated and still efficient and uncorrupted administrator or a freedom fighter and Gandhian martyr who lived for upholding democracy or a leader who worked for uplifting poor and suppressed. However, this study, emphasizing another aspect of Kamaraj's rule, has argued a subtle but strong envisioned social transformation approach underneath the strategies, plans and random welfare measures of Kamaraj as Chief Minister of Tamilnadu, for all but a decade, from 1954 to 1963. His cordial relationship and political influence with the central government allowed him to lead the state in the right path way. He was able to up utilize all the resources for proper progress. By setting aside conservatives, he stood for the progressive in the overall development of Tamilnadu. Gandhi had affected Kamaraj both in his personal life and in public life. According to the dictates of Gandhi, Kamaraj had led a pure and simple life.

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